

Deliverable D9.2.

DIGIECOQUARRY's WEBSITE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101003750

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D9.2	Work Package No.	WP9	Task/s No.	Tasks 9.1, 9.2, 9.3
Work Package Title	DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION				
Linked Task/s Title	Implementation of the Dissemination strategy, implementation of the Communication strategy, implementation of the Exploitation and IP strategy.				
Status		Final			
Dissemination level	PU	PU-PUBLIC			
Due date deliverable	2021-08-31	Submission date	2021-08-31		
Deliverable version	DEQ_D9.2_ANE_V1.1_20210831.doc				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	ANEFA	
Contributors	Organisation	
CÉSAR LUACES FRADES	ANEFA	
LORENA VILADÉS SANTOS	ANEFA	
PAULO ROMERO MARTÍNEZ	ANEFA	
Reviewers	Organisation	
	MAXAM	
	UPM-AI	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.1	2021-08-26	First written completed version of the website

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of contents

Deliverable report	2
Document Contributors	2
Document History	2
Disclaimer	2
Table of contents	3
List of Abbreviations	5
1 Executive Summary	6
2 Introduction	7
2.1 Scope of the deliverable	7
2.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables	7
2.3 Structure of the deliverable	7
2.4 Main pillars of the Digital Marketing Strategy	8
3 Technical characteristics	9
3.1 Full responsive content website	9
3.2 CMS WordPress	9
3.3 Images & videos optimised for a better load	10
3.4 Connection and Data Exchange protected under SSL certificate	10
3.5 SEO Friendly site and Content	10
4 Digiecoquarry's website initial structure	11
4.1 Main menu	12
4.2 Home	13
4.3 What is DEQ?	13
4.4 About us	14
4.5 Objectives	18
4.6 Concept	18
4.7 News	20
4.8 Contact us	23
4.9 Follow us	24
5 Digiecoquarry's website future structure	28
5.1 Main access to IQS platform	28
5.2 Concept	28
5.3 Progress	29
5.4 Media corner	29

5.5	Events	29
5.6	Resources (Dissemination & Downloads)	29
5.7	Capacity Building Programme	29
5.8	Get involved	29
5.9	Other sections	30
6	Traceability between first version and final version of the website	31
7	Conclusions	33
8	Annex XXIV. List of Figures	34
9	Annex XXV. List of Tables	35

List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
PCo	Project Coordinator
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The present report describes the website (<https://www.digiecoquarry.eu/>) which constitutes the main gateway to DIGIECOQUARRY's activities, deliverables, news and events and delineates the motivation behind its concepts.

This website is an informative page and a Media Hub for all the public interested in the subject of the project. According to this strategy, messages will be shaped and delivered in an effective manner using Digital Marketing Strategies.

At this point the web portal contains available information about the project's concept and approach, its objectives, the consortium, the most recent and active related projects as well as some initial news. The evolution of the website will follow the development of DIGIECOQUARRY, to offer an updated version of the project.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled '[D9.2: DIGIECOQUARRY's Website](#)', aims to design the digital platform for communication of the DIGIECOQUARRY project, with the goal to maximise the project's visibility and impact.

With that in mind, this deliverable outlines the approach to (i) effectively communicate the project and disseminate its results, (ii) support and guide the partners for their individual dissemination activities and (iii) continuously deliver a timely information of the actions, deliverables, events, etc.

With this Website, the DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium aims to effectively promote the project and its results to all possible target groups and audiences at national and a European level.

2.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

The DIGIECOQUARRY's Website will serve as the basis for the dissemination, communication, exploitation activities together with WP7 and WP8.

This deliverable will also provide the support for the organization of the project events and workshops and other relevant initiatives linked with the project.

Figure 1. Relationship between WPs.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the "DIGIECOQUARRY's Website" deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 1 – Executive summary: Contains a brief fact sheet about the project.

Section 2 – Introduction: Provides meaningful information with respect to the Website and its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables, integrated in the Digital Marketing Strategy of the project.

Section 3 – Technical characteristics: Explains why this is a full responsive content website, the reasons why it has been developed in CMS WordPress and other technical features.

Section 4 – DIGIECOQUARRY's website initial structure: Presents the main project's assets to be disseminated throughout the project's duration.

Section 5 – DIGIECOQUARRY's website future structure: Identifies the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project's dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign.

Section 6 – Traceability between first version and final version of the website: Describes how will be the evolution of the website by defining the correspondence with the initial version with the completed version once the contents will be available.

Section 7 – Conclusions: Summarises the conclusions of the DIGIECOQUARRY's Website as well as the way forward.

The Annexes include the lists of tables and figures.

2.4 Main pillars of the Digital Marketing Strategy

DIGIECOQUARRY's goal is to develop an innovative an Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) that will increase the sustainable supply of minerals for the construction sector as well as enabling the sustainable extraction of EU's mineral resources in existing and new quarries.

For that, DIGIECOQUARRY will be:

- Maintaining a dynamic website, all kind of contents will be periodically updated. The website will count with technical articles, investigation papers, public deliverables, pieces of news and policies of the sector, initiatives related to the European Commission, events created by this project or other projects with the same objective, workshops, etc. With this methodology it will improve positioning in Google searchers, and while sharing the content through social networks and the newsletter, more visitors will be attracted to the website.
- The DIGIECOQUARRY's website is the main communication and dissemination tool of the project. To maximise the scope of the project, different strategies of digital marketing will be established.
- SEO – (Search Engine Optimization): the traffic of visits to the DIGIECOQUARRY's website will increase progressively throughout the course of the project thanks to the implementation of strategies oriented to organic traffic, always considering the keywords identified for it.
- Social networks: the information hosted in the DIGIECOQUARRY's website, will be used in the social media channels in a way to increase visits and attract newcomers to the project.
- Newsletter: A periodic newsletter will be distributed between the consortium and the public including achievements and innovations of the project that redirect to the website. Newsletter will be also uploaded to the website in a specific section just for them.
- Linkbuilding: It will be able to create synergies between the DIGIECOQUARRY's website and the partners' websites, as well as with other relevant agents and stakeholders of the sector, Horizon Europe projects in the same field encouraging the exchange of links. Instruction to the rest of the partners will be offered with this aim.

ANEFA is responsible for the design, operation and update of the project's web-portal. All partners are required to create links (banners) to the project web-portal on their websites and to contribute with the news to be uploaded as well as to publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organisations.

The DIGIECOQUARRY's portal will be mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project Consortium.

3 Technical characteristics

3.1 Full responsive content website

Responsive web design allows the DIGIECOQUARRY's website to be visible in all devices and platforms (desktops, tablets and phones).

The incorporation of the state-of-the-art techniques in design also creates a quick and intuitive user experience while browsing the website.

DIGIECOQUARRY's identity, based on the three key concepts of the project: Digitalisation, Ecology (biodiversity and environment) and the Aggregates Industry will be the basis for the design of the website.

3.2 CMS WordPress

This is the more used platform when creating the websites. It allows:

FLEXIBILITY: Every system needs to be able to handle custom demands from the customer without the development period extending to the extreme.

EASY TO USE: The website is easy to use. The website works and can be easily worked. It is completely customisable and maintainable by the customer concerning the content. None the less, it has a lot of resources that are easy reading, fact that invites the user of the webpage to stay browsing for a longer time.

PERFORMANCE: A website always needs to work properly. To guarantee a good performance we take all possible issues into account from the start. Everything needs to work as it should. And this website has the correct HTML and CSS to make the maintenance easy and the visualization attractive and practical.

WordPress (WP, WordPress.org) is a free and open-source content management system (CMS) written in PHP and paired with a MySQL or MariaDB database. Features include a plugin architecture and a template system, referred to within WordPress as Themes. WordPress was originally created as a blog-publishing system but has evolved to support other web content types including more traditional mailing lists and forums, media galleries, membership sites, learning management systems (LMS) and online stores. WordPress is used by 41.4% of the top 10 million websites as of May 2021, WordPress is one of the most popular content management system solutions in use. WordPress has also been used for other application domains, such as pervasive display systems (PDS).

"WordPress is a factory that makes webpages" is a core analogy designed to clarify the functions of WordPress: it stores content and enables a user to create and publish webpages, requiring nothing beyond a domain and a hosting service.

WordPress has a web template system using a template processor. Its architecture is a front controller, routing all requests for non-static URIs to a single PHP file which parses the URI and identifies the target page. This allows support for more human-readable permalinks.

WordPress users may install and switch among different themes.

WordPress' plugin architecture allows users to extend the features and functionality of a website.

The WordPress Accessibility Team has worked to improve the accessibility for core WordPress as well as support a clear identification of accessible themes.

WordPress also features integrated link management; a search engine–friendly, clean permalink structure; the ability to assign multiple categories to posts; and support for tagging of posts. Automatic filters are also included, providing standardized formatting and styling of text in posts (for example, converting regular quotes

to smart quotes). WordPress also supports the Trackback and Pingback standards for displaying links to other sites that have themselves linked to a post or an article. WordPress posts can be edited in HTML, using the visual editor, or using one of a number of plugins that allow for a variety of customized editing features.

According to W3Techs, WordPress powers 40% of all the websites on the Internet, including those without a content management system (CMS) or with a custom-coded CMS. Or to put it another way, WordPress powers over one-third of the web! And if you limit the data set to only websites with a known CMS, WordPress' market share gets even more dominant.

Reasons to use wordpress:

- It's open-source software.
- It's the world's most popular CMS.
- There's a huge, friendly Wordpress community.
- Wordpress allows us to scale our project.
- Themes and plugins give us full control over your website.
- We can optimize your website for search engines.
- Wordpress takes security seriously.
- DIGIECOQUARRY owns the website and its content.

3.3 Images & videos optimised for a better load

Website compression makes it possible to reduce the file size of a web file to about 30% or less of its original size before these files get sent to the browser of a user.

This compressed file is then served to the browser of the user which decompresses it automatically to load the full original file in the browser again. Enabling compression is great for improving page speed because the visitors will need to download much smaller web files as the original ones when browsing web pages, which speeds up the download process of these files.

3.4 Connection and Data Exchange protected under SSL certificate

SSL stands for Secure Sockets Layer; this is a global standard security technology that enables encrypted communications between a web browser and a web server. It is utilized by 1 million online business and individuals to decrease the risk of sensitive information.

To create this secure connection, an SSL certificate is installed on a web server and serves to functions:

It authenticates the identity of the website. It encrypts the data that's being transmitted

3.5 SEO Friendly site and Content

At a fundamental level, a SEO-friendly site is one that allows a search engine to explore and read pages across the site. Ensuring a search engine is the first step to establish DIGIECOQUARRY's visibility in the search engine results page.

A disclaimer with the information related to the GDPR compliance adhere the contact questionnaire and is at the footer of the webpage.

4 Digiecoquarry's website initial structure

DIGIECOQUARRY's website has been created to serve as a project content management system.

DIGIECOQUARRY's website is the main online tool to present and disseminate all the results and events under the framework of the project. It will be regularly updated to provide the latest news with the collaboration of all the partners, relevant results and breakthroughs.

The website is carefully designed to address the public and the people interested in the research activities this project is going to do, in the most effective way. It is the easiest way to ensure the visibility of the project for the EU as well for all the public.

DIGIECOQUARRY's website was designed as an interactive tool, as well as a training and learning one, for public information and communication among the partners and the people invested in the project. It will also be a repository for public documents, materials and useful information related to the project.

The structure and design of the website used during the lifetime of DIGIECOQUARRY will be modified to be adapted to needs and the future outcomes of the project.

The current initial simplified structure of the website provides the following content, guidelines and recommendations of the European Commission:

What is DEQ?

About us

- DigiEcoQuarry's Consortium.
- Coordination Team.
 - The coordination Team.
- Partners.
- International Advisory Board (IAB).
- Networking.

Objectives

- Health & Safety and Security.
- Efficiency, Selectivity and Profitability.
- Environmental Impact.
- Social Acceptance.

Concept

- Need and Background.
- Main Challenges In The Aggregates Industry.
 - Health & Safety (H&S) and Security.
 - Efficiency, Selectivity and Profitability of quarrying operations.
 - Environmental Impact.
 - Social Acceptance.

- Fact Sheets.
 - WP1.
 - WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5.
 - WP6.
 - WP7, WP8, WP9, WP10.

News

- Latest news and articles.
 - ANEFA visits HANSON HEIDELBERG.
 - ANEFA visits HOLCIM.
 - DigiEcoQuarry a key project for the digitalisation of the aggregates industry, has been launched.
- Share This Story, Choose Your Platform!.
- Leave a comment.

Contact us

- How Can We Help?
- Follow us in social media.
- Get In Touch.

Links to:

- Facebook.
- LinkedIn.
- Twitter.
- Instagram.
- YouTube.
- Vimeo.

Disclaimer

This simplified structure is a temporary one to avoid blank sections. The future structure is detailed in next clause.

4.1 Main menu

Figure 2. Main menu.

4.2 Home

The homepage is designed to attract the attention of the viewer with the first visual impact. The project logo is clear and visible, and everything is designed with the same colours theme. In this first page the user will find the motto "The future of quarries. A significant breakthrough in process digitalisation and automation capabilities for the aggregates sector".

With this catchy phrase, we encourage the reader to continue browsing through the website.

Figure 3. DIGIECOQUARRY's home page.

4.3 What is DEQ?

This section introduces the main problems of the aggregates sector and presents DIGIECOQUARRY as the solution to them.

Figure 4. What is DEQ?

4.4 About us

This section describes the DIGIECOQUARRY's Consortium. Then the internal organization of the project is explained with the core *Coordination team* presentation with a picture, name, surname, title and post.

Figure 5. DIGIECOQUARRY's Consortium.

Figure 6. Coordination team.

The 25 Partners description shows the whole name, acronym, logo (linked with the Website of each one), a short description and their specific role in the project.

Figure 7. DIGIECOQUARRY's list of partners.

Figure 8. Example of a partner description.

The *Map of the Consortium* is also displayed.

Figure 9. DIGIECOQUARRY's map of the Consortium.

International Advisory Board (IAB) members are also presented, as well as the network of Organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY.

Figure 10. International Advisory Board.

Figure 11. Networking: Organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY.

4.5 Objectives

After a summary of the goals of the project, a full description of the four main objectives (Health & Safety and Security; Efficiency, Selectivity and Profitability; Environmental Impact; Social Acceptance) in a more focused way is provided.

Figure 12. DIGIECOQUARRY's objectives.

4.6 Concept

DIGIECOQUARRY project applies a holistic methodology structured around 10 interrelated work packages (WP), leading to achieve the initiative's specific objectives.

This section provides a full description of DIGIECOQUARRY, laying out the details that were missed in the general description found in the main homepage: *Need and Background*; *Main Challenges In The Aggregates Industry* and *Fact Sheets* with a description of the structure of Work Packages and a short description.

Concept

DIGIECOQUARRY addresses the quarry as a whole (from small up to multi-site quarries), comprising 8 processes:

This figure shows the overall collaboration logics between partners and the performance of data collection throughout the quarrying operation.

The **network of IoT sensors** gathers data about the machines, the materials, the environment and other important parameters on the field. Sensors' data is collected by on-the-field **sub-platforms** and a cloud-based main platform: the **IoT smart mining platform**. This interoperability platform provides the necessary interfaces to accommodate heterogeneous data and offers data storage capacity (data lake) for each site. As such, the main platform enables standardised exchanges of all relevant data with the BIM and sub-platforms (the latter being implemented as a data warehouse including the AI processes and algorithms).

These sensors, sub-platforms, IoT smart platform, BIM models, AI

components and services comprise the **Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS)** (details in section 3.3 System architecture).

The IQS will thus ensure that all the **quarry management is optimised from a global and holistic perspective in quasi real-time**, defining priorities between process interaction, leading to a **decision-making support framework**.

This ensures a **market potential and a competitive advantage** that will be gained through the pilot sites, leading to a business case which can be implemented and replicated across the EU and worldwide in the coming years.

Figure 13. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.

On a global basis, the annual extraction of materials tripled from 1970 to 2017 and it continues to grow. According to the European Raw Materials 2050 roadmap, securing reliable and sustainable access to Raw Materials (RM) and developing domestic value chains are crucial to boosting growth, jobs and competitiveness in Europe. Today the European Union (EU) is dependent on imports of many RM crucial for a strong industrial base.

The aggregates extractive industry provides materials for building and infrastructure industries and it is, by far, the **biggest non-energy extractive industry in the EU**, representing 75-80% of the EU mining and quarrying sector in terms of number of mines/quarries (26,000 sites) and companies (15,000 companies, 98.5% SMEs), and amount of materials supplied (>3 billion Tns/year). It also concentrates **over 40% of the direct jobs** (>220,000 jobs) and **incomes** (>20 billion €/year) of the global EU mining and quarrying sector (see detailed data in FIGURE).

These data show that the aggregates industry is vital for the EU economy. However, in order to **keep this position in the long-term** and to **reduce the dependency on imports** (main objectives of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on RM), the challenges are multidisciplinary: The materials and their production processes need to be **safe and secure**, but also **efficient and profitable**, while having **low environmental and social impacts**, especially for quarries in urban areas. Thus, four groups of challenges have been identified.

EU AGGREGATES INDUSTRY	EU ADDED VALUE
26,000 EXTRACTION SITES	81.26% OF THE TOTAL EUROPEAN MINING AND QUARRYING SITES
15,000 COMPANIES (98.5% SMEs / 1.5% Large)	78.9% OF THE TOTAL EUROPEAN MINING AND QUARRYING COMPANIES
3 BILLION TONS EXTRACTED AND SUPPLIED TO THE EU MARKET	75.6% OF THE TOTAL MINERALS & ROCKS SUPPLIED TO THE EU
220,000 PERSONS DIRECTLY EMPLOYED	42.7% OF THE TOTAL EUROPEAN MINING AND QUARRYING DIRECT JOBS
€20 BILLION TURNOVER ANNUALLY	41.7% OF THE TOTAL EUROPEAN MINING AND QUARRYING TURNOVER

Figure 14. DIGIECOQUARRY's need & background.

Figure 15. DIGIECOQUARRY's main Challenges In The Aggregates Industry.

Figure 16. DIGIECOQUARRY's fact sheets.

4.7 News

This section will be the place where DIGIECOQUARRY's news are posted.

Latest news and articles are always going to be up to date with the main outcomes and the related material useful for the consortium and the community of people interested in the project.

They will be based on the future advances of the project, deliverables, meetings and events partners organise or attend to, workshops, news related to H2020 projects and politics and new strategies de EC generates related to the theme of the project, events other projects related to DIGIECOQUARRY's assist, and pieces of news about the value chain of the research field.

Every partner has the obligation of allowing the other member of the consortium know, the pieces of news they generate this being: the attendance to an event or workshop, the publication of a science paper or anything that could be useful to the communication plan of this project. The website will be up to date by posting at least to pieces of news per month.

Figure 17. Latest news and articles – Headlines.

Figure 18. Option to visualise the pictures.

Figure 19. Full content of a news.

This section offers the option of *Share This Story*, by choosing the *Platform*!

It is also possible to *Leave a comment*.

Figure 20. Options to share the news and to leave a comment.

4.8 Contact us

In the contact us section a form is available to get in touch with the project coordination team.

Figure 21. Contact us section with links to social media and with the mention to the founding of the EC.

Figure 22. Get in touch and How can we help form.

4.9 Follow us

The footer of the website contains de links to the project's social networks: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube and Vimeo.

Figure 23. DIGIECOQUARRY's Facebook.

Figure 24. DIGIECOQUARRY's Twitter.

Figure 25. DIGIECOQUARRY's LinkedIn.

Figure 26. DIGIECOQUARRY's YouTube.

Figure 27. DIGIECOQUARRY's Vimeo.

Figure 28. DIGIECOQUARRY's Instagram.

5 Digiecoquarry's website future structure

As the project evolves, the web portal will be permanently updated and further enriched with all publishable deliverables, promotional material and events. Links to relevant initiatives, to social media accounts of the project and to project partner's webpages are also be included.

ANEFA is responsible for the design, operation and update of the project's web-portal. All partners are required to create links (banners) to the project web-portal on their websites and to contribute with the news to be uploaded as well as to publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organisations.

The DIGIECOQUARRY's portal will be mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project Consortium.

In the coming months, according with the developments and new materials, this simplified structure will be developed to a more complete one (see Figure 1), in order to gather all the information about the project:

Figure 29. DIGIECOQUARRY's final structure of the Website.

In addition to what has already been described in the previous section, as the necessary information is generated, as scheduled in the project, the sections of DIGIECOQUARRY's website will be completed with what is included below:

5.1 Main access to IQS platform

DIGIECOQUARRY's portal will be the main access to the Innovative Quarrying System (IQS).

5.2 Concept

The concept section will be completed with *Technologies*; *Deliverables* (Code/Title/1 paragraph description + download); *Publications*; *Sites & Case studies* and *Related projects*.

5.3 Progress

A new *Progress* section will be developed to gather the latest status of the project.

5.4 Media corner

A new section will consist in different subsections which documents are all downloadable:

- *Newsletters* are going to be posted on the website and highlighting the main outcomes of the project, They will be available in this section as web format and in a pdf. version to download.
- *Press Releases* where it will be possible to find the press releases made by the Consortium of the project.
- *In the Media* (Press clipping) will post the pieces of news about DIGIECOQUARRY project in the general and specialised Media.
- *Gallery* will show relevant photos & videos related with the project (pictures of the consortium and the events that DIGIECOQUARRY will organise or attend to will be posted. All photos will be described with a headline and a short paragraph in a way to let people get into context and are order by Day-Month-Year
- *Documents* and *Presentations* will allow to download other materials for the Media.

5.5 Events

The events published in this section will be based on the future advances of the project, meetings, workshops, and events partners organise or attend to including events from other projects related to DIGIECOQUARRY.

Every partner has the obligation to inform the other member of the consortium their attendance to an event or workshop.

All the information of the events & workshops will be included in the website and in the *Agenda*.

A *Search engine* will allow to find any event.

The registration for the events and workshops organised by DIGIECOQUARRY will be possible from the website.

5.6 Resources (Dissemination & Downloads)

This section will allow to download all the dissemination resources of DIGIECOQUARRY: *Brochures, Leaflets, Posters, Articles* (search engine) and *Other materials* like *Roll-up design, Infographics* or the *Logo* of the project.

5.7 Capacity Building Programme

All the Capacity Building Programme will be available in this section: *Video Tutorials; Training tools* and *Massive Online Open Course – MOOC*.

5.8 Get involved

This section aims to make the link between the project and Stakeholders by:

- A form to *Adhere as interested partner*.
- A form to *Subscribe to DIGIECOQUARRY Newsletter*.
- A *BLOG & online Fora*.
- A form to *Request a demo*.

5.9 Other sections

Other sections of the Website will be:

- Follow us on social media: Facebook / LinkedIn / Twitter / Instagram / YouTube / Vimeo.
- DIGIECOQUARRY PROJECT - CONCEPT (text + visual description with infographics) / AIMS (text + visual description with infographics) / APPROACH (text + visual description with infographics) / IMPACTS (text + visual description with infographics).
- Next Event - Announcement & Registration.
- Access to DIGIECOQUARRY platform.
- Videos.
- Project partner (logos).
- Map.
- International Advisory Board.
- Drone visit to the sites.
- Agenda.
- NEWS (latest news).
- Contact.
- EU Flag “This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101003750”.
- Members only section.

6 Traceability between first version and final version of the website

The traceability between the first version of the site and the final configuration is shown in Table 1.

Initial configuration of www.digiecoquarry.eu	Final configuration of www.digiecoquarry.eu
What is DEQ?	What is DEQ?
About us <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DigiEcoQuarry's Consortium ▪ Coordination Team. Name and mails ▪ Partners (Map, Logo & description & Link) ▪ International Advisory Board ▪ Networking 	About us <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DigiEcoQuarry's Consortium ▪ Coordination Team. Name and mails ▪ Partners (Map, Logo & description & Link) ▪ International Advisory Board ▪ Networking
Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Health & Safety and Security ▪ Efficiency, Selectivity and Profitability ▪ Environmental Impact ▪ Social Acceptance 	Concept <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need and Background ▪ Main Challenges In The Aggregates Industry ▪ Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Health & Safety and Security ○ Efficiency, Selectivity and Profitability ○ Environmental Impact ○ Social Acceptance ▪ Fact Sheets ▪ Technologies ▪ Deliverables (Code/Title/1 paragraph description + download) ▪ Publications ▪ Sites & Case studies ▪ Related projects
Concept <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need and Background ▪ Main Challenges In The Aggregates Industry ▪ Fact Sheets 	
	Progress
News <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Latest news and articles ▪ Share This Story, Choose Your Platform! ▪ Leave a comment 	News <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Latest news and articles ▪ Share This Story, Choose Your Platform! ▪ Leave a comment
	Media Corner <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Newsletters ▪ Press releases ▪ In the Media (Press clipping) ▪ Gallery (Photos & Videos) ▪ Documents ▪ Presentations
	Events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Agenda & search engine
	Resources (Dissemination & Downloads) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brochures ▪ Leaflets ▪ Posters ▪ Articles (search engine) ▪ Other materials (Roll-up design, Infographics or the Logo)
	Capacity Building Programme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Video Tutorials ▪ Training tools ▪ Massive Online Open Course – MOOC

Initial configuration of www.digiecoquarry.eu	Final configuration of www.digiecoquarry.eu
<p>Contact us</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ How Can We Help? ▪ Follow us in social media ▪ Get In Touch 	<p>Get involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Form to adhere as interested partner ▪ Subscribe to DIGIECOQUARRY Newsletter ▪ BLOG & online Fora ▪ Request a demo ▪ Contact us <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How Can We Help? ○ Follow us in social media ○ Get In Touch
<p>Follow us</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facebook ▪ LinkedIn ▪ Twitter ▪ Instagram ▪ YouTube ▪ Vimeo 	<p>Follow us</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facebook ▪ LinkedIn ▪ Twitter ▪ Instagram ▪ YouTube ▪ Vimeo
	Member's login section

Table 1. Evolution of www.digiecoquarry.eu.

7 Conclusions

DIGIECOQUARRY is a digital project that is focusing a large number of aggregates sites across Europe and the World.

The website has to be a powerful tool for dissemination, communication, clustering, capacity building and exploitation, as well as the main access to the Intelligent Quarrying System – IQS. AT the same time, it has to be accessible and user friendly, to facilitate the use by an industry with low digital skills.

Then, it will be strategic for the success of the project to be able to have a proactive management of the website.

8 Annex XXIV. List of Figures

Figure 1. Relationship between WPs.....	7
Figure 2. Main menu.....	12
Figure 3. DIGIECOQUARRY's home page.....	13
Figure 4. What is DEQ?.....	14
Figure 5. DIGIECOQUARRY's Consortium.....	14
Figure 6. Coordination team.....	15
Figure 7. DIGIECOQUARRY's list of partners.....	15
Figure 8. Example of a partner description.....	16
Figure 9. DIGIECOQUARRY's map of the Consortium.....	16
Figure 10. International Advisory Board.....	17
Figure 11. Networking: Organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY.....	17
Figure 12. DIGIECOQUARRY's objectives.....	18
Figure 13. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.....	19
Figure 14. DIGIECOQUARRY's need & background.....	19
Figure 15. DIGIECOQUARRY's main Challenges In The Aggregates Industry.....	20
Figure 16. DIGIECOQUARRY's fact sheets.....	20
Figure 17. Latest news and articles – Headlines.....	21
Figure 18. Option to visualise the pictures.....	22
Figure 19. Full content of a news.....	22
Figure 20. Options to share the news and to leave a comment.....	23
Figure 21. Contact us section with links to social media and with the mention to the founding of the EC.....	23
Figure 22. Get in touch and How can we help form.....	24
Figure 23. DIGIECOQUARRY's Facebook.....	24
Figure 24. DIGIECOQUARRY's Twitter.....	25
Figure 25. DIGIECOQUARRY's LinkedIn.....	25
Figure 26. DIGIECOQUARRY's YouTube.....	26
Figure 27. DIGIECOQUARRY's Vimeo.....	26
Figure 28. DIGIECOQUARRY's Instagram.....	27
Figure 29. DIGIECOQUARRY's final structure of the Website.....	28

9 Annex XXV. List of Tables

Table 1. Evolution of www.digiecoquarry.eu32